

A MODEL FOR BRIDGING CRACK GROWTH IN TITANIUM METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with the description of a crack bridging model utilizing an approach in which the matrix crack is assumed to extend in a discrete manner with each crack extension encompassing one bridging fiber. The debonding length along the first bridging fiber, which is the one farthest away from the crack tip, is determined by considering a length of matrix crack bridged by a fiber and is subjected to the far-field applied stress range. For this purpose, a representative unit cell of a bridging fiber embedded in the matrix phase is isolated for finite element analysis. The debonding length along the bridging fiber is established through an interface debonding criterion. The corresponding fiber traction range is converted into a bridging fiber pressure and introduced as a shielding term in order to calculate the effective matrix crack tip stress intensity factor range for this crack length. This driving force can be viewed as being provided by an effective stress range acting on a homogenized composite specimen with a center crack of total length encompassing 2 bridging fibers, one on each side. Finite element calculations on the cylinder model subjected to this stress range would yield the corresponding fiber traction through external force equilibrium consideration. The traction on the first and second bridging fibers, then, represent the integrated closure pressure distribution along the current bridged crack length. The updated stress intensity factor range for this crack, which include two bridging fibers, can then be calculated and the corresponding effective stress range acting on an equivalent homogenized composite specimen containing this crack is determined. This procedure is repeated for each of the bridging fibers. The limiting condition for the crack propagation is the fiber traction of any of the bridging fibers reaching the fiber failure limit. The fracture of this particular fiber would then reduce the shielding component at the crack tip thus sending the crack growth rate to an increasing rate trend. This transition represents the end of the crack shielding stage.

In order to implement this model an interface debonding criterion is implemented. This criterion assumes that debonding occurs instantaneously along a fiber impinged by an approaching Mode I crack for a length where the shear stress magnitude exceeds the debonding shear strength of the interphase region. Upon initial debonding, frictional shear stress acts between the debonded

interfaces under the compressive radial stress component acting across the interfaces. Further increase in L_i is determined by the interface fracture toughness. This would require the knowledge of the interface crack tip driving force calculated for a given loading condition. In this analysis, the interface crack is assumed to be a pure shear mode crack advancing between two dissimilar materials. The driving force for this crack is derived in terms of the bimaterial elastic constant and the knowledge of the Mode II crack opening displacement measured along the interface crack length. Furthermore, the criterion for crack bridging transition was defined in terms of bridging fiber failure. The failure strength characteristics of the SiC fiber is determined through a series of monotonic tension, residual fatigue strength and fatigue-life tests performed on SCS-6 fibers at room temperature, 500 and 650 °C.

The model was examined by generating the crack growth rate versus applied stress intensity factor for ScS-6/Timetal21S with fiber volume fraction of 30%. The simulations were carried out for load conditions including three temperatures; 25 °C, 500 °C and 650 °C. Results of these simulations are compared with experimental results see the figure below, carried out on the same fiber reinforced composite for the same loading conditions and temperature levels. Results of the comparison were used to determine the validity of the model as a tool for crack growth prediction in composites subjected to high temperature loadings.

